
A STUDY ON EXPECTED SERVICE QUALITY FACTORS BY THE MARKETER IN E-MARKETING IN INDIA

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Abstract:

In the present study, the descriptive research design has been administered. Since this research describes the characteristics of the marketers in e-marketing, it is concerned with descriptive in nature. Meanwhile, this study analyze the e-marketing behavior and its antecedents, e-services quality, service failure in e-marketing, its relationship with the profile of the marketers, it seems to be diagnostic in nature. In total, 535 marketers were identified by popular web service providers namely Pronet, Satyam, Airtel and BSNL. Hence the present study has made an attempt to fill up the research gap with the help of proposed research model.

Keywords: Service Quality; Online Marketer; e-services.

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1. Introduction

In e-marketing the customer value is often held dear too many customers hearts. Values affect customers in determining evaluative criteria. The customer value reflects the ratio between perceived benefits and perceived sacrifices (Morroe, 1990). A reduction in customers cost may be a real contribution of providing the total value to the customers (Best, 1997). The total cost (e.g. time and risk) as well as price will have an impact on the customers' evaluation of alternative offerings and customers satisfaction (Ravald and Gronroos,1996).

For marketers, e-marketing offers a new market place through which to exact the product purchase an delivery process in addition to a physical market place. The major benefits of e-marketing to the marketers are 24 – hours, 365 day opening; lower costs; efficiency gains; extended market reach; quick adjustments to market conditions; influence customer purchases; and improved customer service (Kotler, 2000; Skyrme, 2001). But the e-marketing is subjected with the limitation of lack of physical contact, website and customers, difficulties to capture customers' attentions, staggering volume of information and; more upscale and technical orientation (Cox and Dale, 2001). The e-marketers have to be very careful in the estimation of customer needs and deliver the goods and services according to the need of their customer.

2. Delivery of Service Quality Through E-Marketing

The conceptualization of service quality has its roots in expectancy theory. Many early marketing researchers adopted this theory as the foundation for measuring service quality. (Gronroos, 1984; Parasuraman et al., 1998). One of the first service quality models, called SERVQUAL by Parasuraman et al., 1988 measured service quality using the expectancy disconfirmation framework on the five dimensions of tangibles, responsiveness, reliability, assurance and empathy. In addition, Cronin and Taylor (1992) maintained that expectation was not necessary in measurement of service quality, the conceptualizing their own mode, called SERVPERF.

Lociacono et al., (2000) developed an e-service quality scale called WEBQUAL. This scale focuses on 12 dimensions namely information fit to task, trust, design, visual appeal, flow, business process, interaction fit to task, trust design, visual appeal, flow, business process, interaction response time, intensiveness, innovativeness, integrated communication and substitutability. Yoo and Naveen (2001) named it as SITEQUAL with the measurement of ease of use, processing speed, Aesthetic design and interactive responsiveness. Wombfingbarger and Gilly (2003) measured the e-service quality with the help of website design, customer service, reliability and privacy.

Li et al., (2002) identified the dimension of e-service quality as tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, integration of communication, assurance, quality of information and empathy.

Online can be an effective device for maintaining superior service offerings and creating a higher standard in the retail sector. Service quality of internet retailing spans two primary categories namely (1) customer services; and (2) information system (Yang et al., 2003; Mehta et al., 2000; Cox and Dale, 2001; and Yang et al., 2001). The variables related to service quality in e-marketing have been derived by the previous studies (Doll and Torkzadeh, 1988; Bolfour et al., 1998; Johnson, 1997; Ford et al., 1997 and Mittal et al., 1998).

3. Scope and Need for The Study

The proliferation of and rapid advances in technology – based systems, especially those related to the interest, are leading to fundamental changes in how companies interact with one another and with customers. Indeed, selling products and service via the internet is agreed to have enormous potential, and e-commerce has received enormous pressure, speculation and criticism. The internet technology has the potential to alter almost every aspect of business operations. As a result, it is necessary to take a multidisciplinary approach for understanding the marketers view on e-marketing since the e-marketers act as a intermediaries between the customers and producers of goods and services.

4. Objectives of The Study

- 1) To analyze the various effectiveness of online marketing;
- 2) To evaluate the impact of service quality in online marketing, handless in it on the overall effectiveness of online marketing.

5. Research Methodology

The sampling framework consists of determination of sample size and distribution of sample size. The sampled e-marketers have been identified by the pilot study among 20 experienced and 20 lesser experienced marketers. Since the population of the study is unknown, the sample size of the study is determined by $n = \left[\frac{Z\sigma}{D} \right]^2$. Whereas n - Sample size; Z – 1.96 at five per cent level; σ - Standard deviation of marketers' attitude on e-marketing measured at five point scale in pilot study = 0.5899; and (D)- Error acceptance = 0.05. In the present study, $n = \left[\frac{1.96 \times 0.5899}{.05} \right]^2 = 534.72 = 535$ marketers. In total, 535 marketers was identified by popular web service providers namely Pronet, Satyam, Airtel and BSNL. All 535 marketers have been included as the sampled marketers for the study.

6. Analysis and Interpretation

6.1. Analysis of Exploratory Factor Analysis in Expected Service Quality Factors by the Marketer (IESQFS)

The important expected service quality factors by the marketers have been examined with the help of Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). The test of validity of data for EFA has been conducted with the help of KMO measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of Sphericity. Both these two tests satisfy the validity data for EFA since the KMO measure of sampling adequacy is greater than 0.60 and the chi-square value is significant at five per cent level. The EFA has been executed to narrate the variables into important service quality factors. The result of EFA is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Important Expected Service Quality by the marketers (IESQFs)

Sl.No.	IESQFs	Number of variables in	Eigen value	Per cent of variation explained	Cumulative per cent of variation explained
1	Design	6	5.1682	23.49	23.49
2	Functionality	5	4.2908	19.50	42.99
3	Content	5	3.6418	16.55	59.54
4	Originality	3	2.9011	13.19	72.73
5	Professionalism	3	2.8664	13.02	85.75
	Total	22			
KMO measure of sampling adequacy: 0.7909.			Bartlett's test of sphericity: Chi-Square value: 93.94*		

*Significant at five per cent level

The important service qualities needed by the marketers are design, functionality, content, originality and professionalism. The narrated five IESQFs explain the service quality variables needed by the marketer to the extent of 71.29 per cent. The important IESQFs is 'design' since its eigen value and per cent of variation explained by it are 5.1682 and 28.49 per cent respectively.

The next two IESQFs are functionality and content since its eigen values are 4.2908 and 3.6418 respectively. The per cent of variation explained by them are 19.50 and 16.55 per cent respectively. The last two IESQFs are originality and professionalism since its eigen values are 2.9011 and 2.8644 respectively. The per cent of variation explained by them are 13.19 and 13.02 per cent respectively which is similar the findings of Novak et al., (2000) and; Sheehan and Hoy (2000).

6.2. Reliability and validity of variables in IESQFs

The variables in each IESQFs are varying from 6 to 3 variables. Since the variables in each IESQFs explain it, the present study has made an attempt to examine the reliability and validity of variables in each IESQF with the help of Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). It results in standardized factor loading, it's 't' statistics, composite reliability and average variance extracted. The results are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Reliability and validity of variables in IESQFs

Sl.No.	IESQFs	Range of standardized factor loading	Range of t – statistics	Cronbach alpha	Composite reliability	AVE in per cent
1	Design	0.9044 – 0.7219	4.0172* - 2.7817*	0.8108	0.7803	59.14
2	Functionality	0.8709 – 0.6645	3.7084* - 2.5502*	0.7204	0.7019	50.08
3	Content	0.9012 – 0.7209	4.0121* - 3.1012*	0.7467	0.7245	54.08
4	Originality	0.8646 – 0.7104	3.5511* - 2.8033*	0.7349	0.7117	53.14
5	Professionalism	0.8876 – 0.7011	3.7617* - 2.4541*	0.7603	0.7508	56.17

*Significant at five per cent level

The standardized factor loading of the variables in each IESQFs are greater than 0.60 which reveals the content validity. The 't' statistics of the standardized factor loading of the variables in IESQFs are significant at five per cent level which indicates its convergent validity. It is also supported by the composite reliability and average variance explained since these are greater than its minimum threshold of 0.50 and 50.00 per cent respectively. The cronbach alpha of each IESQFs are greater than 0.70. It reveals that the included variables in each IESQFs explain it to the minimum extent of 70.00 per cent.

6.3. Marketers view on IESQFs

The marketers view on important service quality needed b them are examined with the help of the mean score of the five IESQFs. The score of each IESQFs is derived by the mean score of the variables in it. The mean score of each IESQFs among the LE and HE marketers have been computed separately. The 't' test has been administered to find out the significant difference

among the two group of marketers regarding their view on IESQFs. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Marketers' view on IESQFs

Sl.No.	IESQFs	Mean score among marketers in		t – statistics
		LE	HE	
1	Design	3.1400	3.8828	-3.3891*
2	Functionality	3.3884	3.9611	-2.0128*
3	Content	3.5896	3.8996	-0.6965
4	Originality	3.4551	3.8059	-1.6081
5	Professionalism	3.1986	3.9032	-3.4548*

*Significant at five per cent level

The highly viewed IESQFs among the LE marketers is content and originality since their mean scores are 3.5896 and 3.4551 respectively. Among the HE marketers, these are functionality and professionalism since their mean scores are 3.8996 and 3.9032 respectively. Regarding the perception on IESQFs, the significant difference among LE and HE marketers have been noticed in the case of perception on design, functionality and professionalism since their respective 't' statistics are significant at five per cent level.

6.4. Discriminant IESQFs among the LE and HE Marketers

The perceptions on IESQFs among the LE marketers differ from the HE marketers. It is imperative to identify the important discriminant IESQFs among the two group of marketers for some policy implications. The two group discriminant analysis has been administered. Initially, the mean difference and its 't' statistics have been computed. The discriminant power has been computed with the help of wilks lambda. The results are given in Table 4.

Table 4: Mean difference and discriminant power of IESQFs among Lesser and Higher Experienced

Sl.No.	IESQFs	Mean score among marketers in		Mean difference	t – statistics	Wilks Lambda
		LE	HE			
1	Design	3.1400	3.8828	-0.7428	-3.3891*	0.1233
2	Functionality	3.3884	3.9611	-0.5727	-2.0128*	0.1644
3	Content	3.5896	3.8996	-0.3100	-0.6965	0.4996
4	Originality	3.4551	3.8059	-0.3508	-1.6081	0.3548
5	Professionalism	3.1986	3.9032	-0.7046	-3.4848*	0.1018

*Significant at five per cent level

The significant mean differences are noticed in the case of design, functionality and professionalism since their respective 't' statistics are significant at five per cent level. The higher mean differences are noticed in the case of design and professionalism since their mean differences are -0.7428 and -0.7046 respectively. The higher discriminant power is identified in the case of professionalism and designs since their respective wilks lamda are 0.1018 and 0.1233. The significant IESQFS have been included for the establishment of two group discriminant function.

The unstandardized procedure has been followed to estimate the function. The estimation function is:

$$Z = 0.5142 + 0.1649x_1 - 0.1433x_2 - 0.2199x_6$$

The relative contribution of discriminant IESQFs in total discriminant score is identified by the product of discriminant coefficient and the mean difference of the respective IESQFs. The results are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Relative Contribution of IESQFs in TDS

Sl.No.	IESQFs	Discriminant coefficient	Mean difference	Product	Relative contribution in TDS
1	Design	-0.1649	-0.7425	0.1224	34.06
2	Functionality	-0.1433	-0.5727	0.0821	22.85
3	Professionalism	-0.2199	-0.7046	0.1549	43.09
	Total			0.3263	100.00
Per cent of cases correctly classified: 78.91.					

The higher discriminant coefficients are identified in the case of professionalism since its coefficient is -0.2189. It shows the higher influence of above said IESQFs in the discriminant function. The higher relative contribution in Total Discriminant Score is identified in the case of 'professionalism' since its relative contribution is 43.09 per cent. The estimated two group discriminant function correctly classifies the cases to the extent of 78.91 per cent. The analysis reveals that the important discriminant of LE and HE marketers is their view on professionalism which is highly viewed by the HE marketers than the LE marketers.

7. Summary of Findings

The service qualities in online marketing delivered by the marketers are studied with the help of 41 variables. The important service quality factors narrated by factor analysis are reliability, ease of use, communication, responsiveness, personalization, convenience, creditability, courtesy continuous important access and security. The highly delivered service quality factors by LE and HE marketers are continuous improvement and credibility. Regarding the delivery of service quality factors, the significant difference among the LE and HE have been noticed in their case of eight out eleven service quality factors. The significantly associating important profiles of marketers regarding their delivery of service quality factors are business turnover, market coverage and technology readiness score. The important discriminant service quality factors among the LE and HE are personalization and continuous improvement which are highly LE compared to HE marketers.

8. Recommendations

Confidence Building on Online Marketing: The present study reveals that the lacks of confidence on online marketing among the marketers affect the level of effectiveness of online marketing. In order to extent the online marketing in all fields, first of all, the mind blocks of the marketers have been removed. It is possible only by the experienced marketers. The new marketers

felt some inconveniences and risk in the online marketing. These inconveniences and risk can be eliminated by appropriate counseling to the new marketers by the experienced marketers. It will increase the application of online marketing in all fields.

Online Marketing Service Quality: Since the service quality in online marketing influence it's effectiveness, it is advised to enrich the service quality continuously by the marketers. In order to perform well in the online marketing, the marketers should enrich their service quality especially in design, functionality, extent, originality and professionalism. The above said service quality factors have to be updated as per the requirement of the customers in the marketers. This can be possible when the marketers have to study the service quality in online marketing at the international level and the services offered by the multinational companies through the online.

9. Conclusion

The dominant number of products dealt by the marketers is two or three whereas the higher business turnover is noticed among higher experienced compared to lesser experienced. The dominant market coverage among the lesser and higher experienced marketers are zonal and national respectively. The level of of electronic commerce (EC) adoption is higher among the highly experienced marketers compared to lesser experienced marketers. The significantly associating profile of marketers and their level of electronic commerce adoption are their age, level of education, personality, business turnover, and market coverage and technology readiness.

References

- [1] Balfour, A., Farquhar, B and Langmann, G (1998), "The consumer needs in global electronic commerce", *Electronic Markets*, 8(2), pp.9-12.
- [2] Best, R (1997), *Marketing Based Management*, Prentice-Hall International, Englewood Cliffs, NJ.
- [3] Cox, J and Dale, B.G (2001), "Service quality and e-commerce: an exploratory analysis", *Managing Service Quality*, 11(2), pp.121-131.
- [4] Cox, J and Dale, B.G (2001), "Service quality and e-commerce; an exploratory analysis," *Managing Service Quality*, 11(2), pp.121-131.
- [5] Cronin, J. Joseph and Steven A. Taylor, "Measuring Service Quality: A Reexamination and Extension", *Journal of Marketing*, 56, July 1992, pp.55-68.
- [6] Doll, N.J and Torkzadeh, G (1994), "A confirmatory factor analysis of the end-user computing satisfaction instrument", *MIS Quarterly*, 18(December), pp.443-461.
- [7] Ford, R.C., Bach and Fostler, M.D (1997), "Methods of measuring patient satisfaction in health care organization", *Health Care Management Review*, 22(2), pp.74-89.
- [8] Gronross, Christian, (1982) *Strategic Management and marketing in the service sector* Helsingfors: Swedish of Economics and Business Administration,
- [9] Johnson, R (1995), "The determinants of service quality: Satisfier and dissatisfies", *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, 8(5), pp.53-71.
- [10] Kotler, P (2000), *Marketing Management*, International edition, Prentice-Hall, Englewood cliffs, NJ.
- [11] Li. Y.N., K.C. Tan and M. Xie, (2002) "Measuring Web-Based Service Quality", *Total Quality Management*, 13(5), pp.685-700.
- [12] Lociacono, Eleanor, (2000) Richard T-Watson, and DaleGoodhne, "Webqual: A website quality instrument", Working paper, Worcester Polytechnic Institute,

- [13] Mehta, S.C., Lalwani, A.K and Han, S.C (2000), “Service quality in retailing: relative efficiency of alternative measurement scale for different product-service environments”, *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management*, 28(2), pp.62-72.
- [14] Morroe, K.B (1990), *Pricing – Making profitable decisions*, McGraw – Hill, New York, NY.
- [15] Mittal, v., Ross, W.T and Baldasare, P.M (1998), “The asymmetric impact of negative and positive attribute–level performance on overall satisfaction and re purchase intentions”, *Journal of Marketing*, 62(January), pp. 33-47.
- [16] Novak, T.P., Hoffman, O.L., and Yung, Y., (2000), “Measuring the customer experience in online environments: A structural modeling approach”, *Marketing Science*, 19(Winter), pp.22-42.
- [17] Parasuraman, A., (1988) Valarie, A. Zeithaml and Lemand L. Berry, “SERVQUAL: A multiple item scale for measuring customer perceptions of service quality”, *Journal of Retailing*, 64(1), , pp.12-40.
- [18] Ravald, A and Gronvoos, C (1996), “The value concept and relationship marketing,” *European Journal of marketing journal of marketing*, 30(2), pp.19-30.
- [19] Sheehan, K.B., and Hoy, M.G., (2000), “Dimension of Privacy concern among online consumers”, *Journal of Public Policy and Marketing*, 19(Spring), pp.62-73.
- [20] Skyrme, D.J (2001), *Capitalizing on knowledge from e-commerce to K-business*, Butterworth – Heinemann, Oxford.
- [21] Wolfenbarger, Mary F and Mary C. Gilly, (2002) “Comq: Dimensionalizing, measuring and predicting quality of the e-tail experience”, Working Paper, No.02-100, Marketing science institute, Cambridge.
- [22] Yang, Z., Peterson, R.T and Huang, L (2001), “Taking the pulse of internet pharmacies: online consumers speak out on pharmacy services”, *Marketing Health Services*, 21(2), pp.4-10.
- [23] Yoo, Boonghee and Naveen Donthu, (2001) “Developing a scale to measure the perceived quality of an internet shopping site (site equal)”, *Quarterly Journal of Electronic commerce*, 2(1), pp.31-46.
- [24] Zhilin Yang, Rohin T. Peterson and Shoochan cai (2003), “Service quality dimension of internet retailing: an exploratory analysis”, *Journal of Service Marketing*, 17(7), pp.685-700.

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